

Models of Information Seeking Behaviour.

Information Seeking Behaviour is a procedure in which certain approaches or steps are followed by a user to get needed information.

Different scholars have identified these steps of users in their own way and arranged it in a framework to formulate various information seeking behaviour models.

Some of these models are-

1. Willson's Problem- solving model (1981)

Fig: Wilson's Problem-solving model (available via licence: CC BY)

(https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Wilsons-1981-information-behaviour-model_fig1_336932757)

Wilson states that, a user's information need is not a primary need but a secondary need. Willson's model of information seeking behaviour, also known as Wilson's problem- solving model. According to this model, information seeking emerges when a user feels need of information. To satisfy his/her need they makes demands upon information sources (formal &informal) and services.

If the user is satisfied with the results, then the information is used, exchanged and transferred to others. If the result is failure in satisfy the need, then the searching process starts again.

Wilson's revised model (1996)

David Wilson's model of information-seeking behaviour, established in 1996, serves as a foundational framework for understanding how individuals seek, process and utilize information. It builds upon his earlier work (1981) and synthesizes theories from psychology, sociology and information science.

1. Information Need

The journey commences with the acknowledgment of a demand for knowledge, which serves as the main impetus for engaging in information-seeking behaviours. The necessity for information emerges when there exists a discrepancy between the existing level of knowledge and the required knowledge to address an issue or make a choice. This "discrepancy" may arise from:

- Cognitive ambiguity.
- A quest for clarity or enhancement of knowledge.
- A requirement to resolve practical challenges in professional, health, or personal realms.

2. Intervening Variables

These are elements that either promote or obstruct an individual's capability to efficiently seek information. Wilson's framework broadly classifies these factors:

Psychological variables:

Motivation: Intrinsic (personal curiosity) or extrinsic (work or academic obligations).

Emotions: Stress or anxiety can either hinder or motivate information-seeking initiatives.

Demographic variables:

Age, gender, educational background, income bracket, or cultural heritage.

These characteristics affect preferences, accessibility, and the ability to utilize information systems.

Environmental variables:

Physical access to information locations (libraries, databases, internet).

Time limitations and financial constraints available for information-seeking.

Social variables:

Influence from peers, family, or organizational ethos.

Social norms or perceived acceptability of seeking assistance from certain sources.

Source-related factors:

Perceived reliability, relevance, or trustworthiness of information sources.

3. Activating Mechanisms

These mechanisms elucidate why and how individuals commence information-seeking endeavours. Wilson utilizes various theoretical perspectives:

Stress and Coping Theory (Lazarus and Folkman, 1984):

Information-seeking acts as a coping mechanism to alleviate stress induced by uncertainty or knowledge deficiencies. An individual is more inclined to pursue information if they believe it will effectively lessen stress.

Risk/Reward Theory:

Individuals assess the investment of effort, time, and potential dangers associated with information-seeking against the anticipated advantages or rewards of acquiring the information. Greater perceived benefits amplify the likelihood of engaging in information-seeking conduct.

4. Information-Seeking Behaviour

This refers to the concrete steps undertaken to locate and obtain information. It may include:

Active Search: Direct interaction with information sources, such as exploring online databases, consulting literature, or reaching out to specialists.

Passive Search: Discovering information by chance without actively seeking it, such as through social media or informal dialogues.

Passive Attention: Absorbing information inadvertently, such as overhearing discussions.

Ongoing Search: Ongoing, exploratory inquiry as part of a sustained interest or necessity.

5. Information Processing and Use

Once information is gathered, the individual appraises it for:

- Relevance: Does it satisfy the original need?
- Precision and Reliability: Is the source dependable?
- Utilization: Can the information be employed to resolve the issue or bridge the knowledge discrepancy?
- After assessment, the individual integrates the information into their knowledge framework or applies it to their circumstances.

6. Iterative Processes

The model acknowledges the cyclical essence of information-seeking behaviour:

- Successes or failures in locating pertinent information can generate new information needs.
- Revisions may be made to methods or sources based on past experiences.
- Contentment with the outcomes might conclude the process, or dissatisfaction may trigger additional searches.

Fig: Wilson's model of information behaviour (uploaded by Tom Wilson)

(https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Wilsons-1996-model-of-information-behaviour_fig4_228784950)

2.Dervin's sense-making model

Brenda Dervin's sense-making model was published in 1983. According to her, users go through different stages in making sense of the world. In the first stage, the need for information arises, she calls it a situation. People find a gap between their current understanding and the knowledge they need to know in order to make sense of the current situation. These gaps are bridged by formulation of questions. So, according to Dervin, four constituent elements are required in implementing Human Information Behaviour:

1. A Situation, which stands for the conditions in which information need arises.

2. A Gap, which identifies the difference between the contextual situation and the desired situation.

3. The outcome represents the use of information to complete a task.

4. A bridge, that is, some means of closing the gap between situation and outcome. To bridge the gap, individuals seek information to make new sense and use this information to help them in everyday life.

Dervin presents these elements in terms of a triangle factors: situation, gap/bridge, and outcome-

Fig: Dervin's sense-making model (uploaded by Rebecca Price)

(https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Sensemaking-framework-Adapted-from-Dervin-1992_fig1_319667732)

3.Savolainen's ELIS model

The Everyday Life Information Seeking (ELIS) model—crafted by Reijo Savolainen in 1995—is an essential framework within the domain of information science. This model investigates how individuals seek, use and process information during their everyday lives, particularly in non-work scenarios, such as at home or during leisure activities. It emphasizes the social and situational factors that influence how people engage with information in their daily existence.

Way of life

“Way of life” refers to an individual's values, routines, and roles, which shape their daily activities and interactions.

- People's everyday information-seeking behaviour is influenced by their "way of life," which includes their values, routines, and roles in society.
- Socioeconomic status, education, and personal interests are important determinants.

Mastery of life

Mastery of life is the ability to organize and manage one's daily life, including solving problems and making decisions.

- This refers to how individuals manage and organize their daily lives, including problem-solving and decision-making.
- Information-seeking is seen as a tool to help people maintain control and adapt to challenges.

Habitual Information-Seeking

- Many information-seeking behaviours are routine and shaped by individuals' social networks, personal preferences, and established habits.

Context and Situation

- Information-seeking behaviour is situational and varies based on specific needs and environments.
- Everyday contexts (e.g., shopping, healthcare, hobbies) significantly influence the kind of information sought.

Sources of Information

- Both formal (e.g., libraries, professionals) and informal (e.g., friends, family, media) sources are used.

- Preference for sources depends on accessibility, trustworthiness, and relevance to the individual.

Fig: Savolainen's ELIS model (uploaded by Aurora Gonzalez-Teruel)

https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Everyday-Life-Information-Seeking-model-Savolainen-1995-p268_fig1_339364109

4. Ellis's model

Ellis's model of information seeking behaviour is a set of stages followed during information seeking by a user. These stages are:

- Starting: beginning of the information-seeking process
- Chaining: following the links of citations, bibliographies obtained from sources of information
- Browsing: consists of undirected and semi-structured searching for information
- Differentiating: clarify the obtained information
- Monitoring: tracking the recent developments in the user's field of interest
- Extracting: sort out the relevant information from a source
- Verifying: inspect the correctness of information
- Ending: carry out a final search to complete the process

5. Kulthau's Information Seeking Process model (1991)

The ISP model portrays users' experiences during information-seeking as a continuum of thoughts (which can initially be uncertain, vague and ambiguous). However, these thoughts gradually evolve; they become clearer, increasingly focused and more specific as the search process unfolds. This transformation occurs because users engage deeply with their queries, although some may encounter obstacles along the way. Actions accompanying these thoughts also play a crucial role in shaping the overall experience.

According to her, information search process has six stages:

- Task initiation - When an individual first recognizes (or becomes conscious of) a deficiency in knowledge or comprehension—often accompanies feelings of uncertainty and apprehension.
- Topic selection - When a general area, topic, or problem is identified—often leads to initial uncertainty, which can give rise to a brief sense of optimism and a readiness to embark on the search.
- Pre-focus exploration - Exploration can become challenging (and often frustrating) when one encounters inconsistent or incompatible information; this situation frequently leads to heightened uncertainty, confusion and doubt. People may find themselves—because of this- “in the dip” of confidence.

- Focus formulation - Formulation represents a stage wherein a concentrated perspective emerges and uncertainty gradually diminishes as confidence starts to build.
- Information collection - Collection involves the gathering of information relevant to the focused perspective, resulting in a decrease in uncertainty as interest and involvement deepen.
- Search closure or presentation - Presentation marks the completion of the search, yielding a new understanding that enables the individual to articulate his or her learning to others, or to utilize that knowledge in some capacity.

Fig: Kuhlthau's ISP model

(<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Saeed-Amini-5/publication/324975386/figure/fig1/AS:623130234073089@1525577233635/Kuhlthaus-Model-of-the-Information-Search-Process.png>)

6. Belkin's ASK model

This model is proposed by Belkin and his associates Oddy, Brooks, Cool and Theil in 1986.

An Anomalous State of Knowledge (ASK) represents a condition wherein an individual recognizes that their existing knowledge is inadequate, insufficient to tackle a particular problem or fulfil a curiosity (this realization can be quite unsettling). Consequently, this anomaly prompts a quest for information.

Stages in the ASK Process

The ASK model does not dictate strict stages; however, it proposes a flow that generally encompasses:

Recognition of Anomaly:

The user becomes aware of a knowledge gap or inconsistency (this could be triggered by a specific task, problem, or context).

Initiation of Information-Seeking:

The user embarks on the journey of seeking information, often with vague or incomplete queries. Although initial searches may be exploratory, they are intended to grasp the scope of the problem.

Interaction and Query Refinement:

Interaction with information systems or sources plays a crucial role in assisting users to refine their understanding of their needs. Feedback loops enable users to adjust their strategies and queries effectively.

Evaluation and Application:

The user evaluates the retrieved information for relevance and usefulness. Because the ASK is resolved, the process concludes; but if it is not resolved, further iterations may ensue.

Fig: Belkin's ASK model

<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/User-oriented-Ir-Research-Approaches-Approaches/f5d4623a28b35970717175bf3deaffe38a404ffc/figure/0>

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